

TRACHEMYS SCRIPTA IN THE EAST AND SOUTH EUROPEAN REGION. A REVIEW OF THE INVASION EXTENT

FLORINA STĂNESCU, TIBOR SOS*, CIPRIAN SAMOILĂ, DAN COGĂLNICEANU

Faculty of Natural and Agricultural Sciences, Ovidius University, Constanța, Romania | Chelonia Romania | *Milvus Group - Bird and Nature Protection Association

Background

Reptilia: Testudines: Emydidae: *Trachemys scripta* (The Common Slider)

Trachemys scripta (photo © Tibor Sos)

- Rank within the 100 of the World's Worst Invasive Alien Species: **93**
- Native to: North America
- Major pathway of introduction in Europe: pet-trade

Materials and methods

- East and South European Region/ ESENIAS countries: Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Kosovo, FYR Macedonia, Montenegro, Serbia, Slovenia, Romania, Turkey.
- Literature review: Adamopoulou & Legakis 2016; Bódis et al. 2012; Çiçek & Ayaz (2015); Crescente et al. 2014; Dimancea 2013; Đorđević & Anđelković 2015; Ficetola et al. 2002; Ficetola et al. 2009; Glavas et al. 2016; Jelić 2014; Jelić & Jelić 2015; Jelić et al. 2016; Kirbis et al. 2016; Krizmanić et al. 2015; Luiselli et al. 1997; Puky et al. 2004; Standfuss et al. 2016; Tzankov et al. 2015; Urosevic 2014; Vamberger et al. 2012; Žagar et al. 2013.
- Citizen science: Herping Romania, *Trachemys* Adoption - Romanian Coalition, Pasari Romania
- Field surveys, unpublished data, personal communications.

Results and discussion

- 589 occurrence records, 106 unique 10 x 10 km grid cells;
- Main habitats: natural/artificial lakes and ponds, channels, estuaries, rivers, streams, recreational areas, wetlands;
- Breeding in the wild: in 5 of the 11 countries where it is present (see figure);
- Possibly breeding in the wild: Greece, Hungary, Romania.

Figure. *Trachemys scripta* distribution within the East and South European Region.